

The Distribution and Chemistry of Formaldehyde Around TW Hydrae

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—by—

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Contents

Abstract	ii
Acknowledgements	iii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Protoplanetary Disks	2
1.2 Chemical Structure of Protoplanetary Disks	3
1.3 Formaldehyde’s Role in Disk Chemistry	4
1.4 TW Hydrae: A Prototypical Disk	7
1.5 Project Goals and Outline	8
2 Observations	10
2.1 Radio Interferometry	10
2.2 ALMA Observations	13
2.3 Data Reduction	15
2.4 Data Products	17
3 Toy Models	20
3.1 Temperature and Density Profiles	22
3.2 Abundance Profiles	26
3.3 Radiative Transfer	27
3.4 Synthetic Observations	29
4 Discussion and Conclusions	35
4.1 Formation Pathway of Formaldehyde	35
4.2 Comparison with CO Snowline Location	36
4.3 Comparison with Dust Location	38
4.4 Conclusions	39
4.5 Future Work	40
References	41

Abstract

The study of the chemistry of protoplanetary disks has broad implications for our understanding of planet compositions and the availability of the conditions necessary for life. Formaldehyde (H_2CO), an early precursor of complex organic molecules (COMs), is an important piece of this chemical puzzle. However, it is unclear by which pathway(s) H_2CO is formed in disks: both gas-phase pathways (important close to the star) and grain-surface pathways (important at and outside the CO snowline) are possible. We present high-resolution synthesized beam $0.51'' \times 0.48''$ or 28×26 AU) ALMA observations of the $3_{12} \rightarrow 2_{11}$ line of *o*- H_2CO in the nearby transition disk TW Hydrae. By searching for an abundance profile consistent with the observations, we constrain the location and thereby the dominant formation pathway of H_2CO . We find that H_2CO emission forms a ring with an inner radius of about 10 AU. The central gap and increasing abundance with radius points to a grain-surface dominated chemistry. The inferred inner radius disagrees with the CO snowline location previously measured in TW Hya of 30 AU, but can be explained by the formation of thin layers of CO on water ices which can occur well inside this radius. Observations of a wider sample of disks will be necessary to determine which disk properties lead to different contributions from gas-phase and grain-surface H_2CO production in general.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Consider humanity’s origin story, and how well science has been able to reconstruct it. Based on today’s understanding, a comprehensive answer to the question “How did we get here?” would include knowledge carefully collected by the fields of cosmology, physics, astronomy, chemistry, geology, biology, and many more. Across a timeline stretching all the way back to the Big Bang, these various scientific disciplines have together provided a fairly complete picture of why the universe is the way it is and how humanity fits into this picture. The story of our origins starts with the formation of fundamental particles, then atoms, then stars and galaxies. It ends with the gradual development of life over several billion years (Allwood et al. (2009) present evidence for life from ~ 3.5 Gyr ago).

There is, however, a gap in this story, between the formation of the Solar System and the rise of life, that is not as well-understood as the other pieces of the puzzle. This period in our history—around the time the Sun and the Earth formed—is the time when the chemistry that eventually seeded life is supposed to have arisen. There are many unanswered questions about this period: How did the chemical precursors to life form? Where did they form, and how were they delivered to Earth? How common are the building blocks of life in other planetary systems?

To begin to answer these questions and questions like them, it is useful to study the birthplace of planets: protoplanetary disks.

1.1 Protoplanetary Disks

Protoplanetary disks are disks of gas and solids (referred to as “dust” or “pebbles”) commonly found orbiting newly formed stars (see, e.g., Beltrán & de Wit, 2016), and are named as such because they host the material out of which planets form. They are believed to be a ubiquitous byproduct of star formation—when a cloud of gas and dust collapses to form a star, there is some leftover material that forms a disk due to conservation of angular momentum (see Shu & Adams, 1987; Wolstencroft & Walker, 1988; Krumholz, 2015). Assuming disks inherit their gas-to-dust ratios from the interstellar medium, their gas masses are about 100 times those of the dust (Draine et al., 2007). An overwhelming majority of the gas is molecular hydrogen, but trace abundances (i.e., abundances on the order of 10^{-4} and below) of other gaseous species are known to exist in disks. (The abundance X of a species A is defined as the ratio of its density to that of hydrogen: $X = n_A/n_{\text{H}_2}$.) The composition of the dust grains is not yet fully constrained, but their major components are thought to be amorphous silicates and carbonaceous materials (Draine, 2003, 2004; Li, 2005). These grains may also possess icy surfaces composed of frozen volatiles such as CO, CO₂, and/or H₂O, to name a few prevalent examples.

Protoplanetary disks last for a median time of $\lesssim 3$ Myr, with nearly all disks clearing away after ~ 6 Myr (Haisch et al., 2001). By the time a disk is cleared away, one or several planets may have formed directly from the coagulation and accretion of this material. The composition of disk material is initially set by the parent molecular cloud, followed by subsequent chemical processing which occurs in the disk itself (Pontoppidan & Blevins, 2014). In general, protoplanetary disk environments drastically influence the process and outcomes of planet formation, especially in the terrestrial planet-forming region ($R \lesssim 10$ AU) (Ida & Lin, 2004; Kretke & Lin, 2012; Mordasini et al., 2012a,b). Understanding how disks evolve with time is thus essential to building intuition on planetary formation and compositions.

1.2 Chemical Structure of Protoplanetary Disks

At a reasonable distance from the star ($R \gtrsim 20$ AU), there are three main zones of chemistry in protoplanetary disks (see Figure 1.1), shaped by the local physical conditions. In the upper layers of the disk, an influx of UV photons promote the existence of ionic, atomic, and radical species, driving ion-neutral and radical chemistry in a tenuous atmosphere ($\rho \lesssim 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$). The temperature of these regions can be on the order of 100 K. In the cold (some tens of K), midplane of the disk, material is shielded from radiation, temperatures are much lower, and chemistry primarily occurs on the surfaces of icy grains. Between these two regimes, a warm (nearly 100 K) molecular layer hosts a rich gas-phase chemistry. In addition to these three layers, the warmest regions of the disk close to the star ($R \lesssim 1$ AU) can also reach high enough gas densities and temperatures to see three-body interactions become an important process. See Section 1 of Chapter 3 for more discussion on the physical parameters present in disks, as well as Henning & Semenov (2013) for a more comprehensive review of the chemical processes.

Figure 1.1 — Schematic of a protoplanetary disk.

In general, the rate at which chemical processes occur in the gas phase is strongly related to the gas density, so gas-phase chemistry is much more important in the inner regions of disks. Chemistry can also occur between molecules sliding on the icy surfaces of grains. Ices on grains are formed by the adsorption, or “freeze-out,” of volatile molecules from the gas phase. Due to the strong dependence of temperature on radius, each species will exist mostly in the solid phase outside of a certain radius. These radii are called “snowlines.” The snow line of CO, for example, occurs when the gas temperature drops below 20 K, which occurred at $R \sim 20$ AU in the disk that formed the Solar System. Therefore, grain-surface chemistry is more prevalent in the outer regions of disks, and nonexistent in the hot inner regions.

Molecules that form on the surfaces of grains can then enter the gas phase via one of several different desorption pathways. If the temperature of the disk is warm enough for a given species, it can sublime, or thermally desorb, directly off of grains. There are also non-thermal pathways for achieving enough energy to come off of grains, including chemical desorption (when a species desorbs from a grain upon its formation); UV photon-induced desorption, which has been well-studied in the laboratory; and processes such as cosmic ray-induced or electron-induced desorption, for which the rates of occurrence are not yet well-known, although there are some estimates (e.g., from Hasegawa & Herbst, 1993; Najita et al., 2001). Whatever the mechanism, molecules that desorb off grains into the gas phase are then available for detection by observing their rotational transitions.

1.3 Formaldehyde’s Role in Disk Chemistry

A key species in understanding the organic chemistry in protoplanetary disks is formaldehyde (H_2CO). Formaldehyde is thought to be a key building block of complex organic molecules, or COMs (Garrod et al., 2008; Herbst & van Dishoeck, 2009; Mumma & Charnley, 2011; Garrod, 2013), including methanol (CH_3OH). For example, formaldehyde is a potential precursor to meteoritic amino acids (Miller, 1957; Peltzer et al., 1984). However, it has not

yet been possible to reliably detect the more complex reaction products of H_2CO in disks. This is due to a combination of factors: lower individual abundances of complex organics, their more refractory nature (they do not readily desorb into the gas phase), and their less populated rotational transitions. In lieu of direct observations of large carbon- and oxygen-bearing molecules, studying the formation of formaldehyde—a vital precursor—will aid in understanding their formation chemistry, location, and subsequent chemical processing.

There are multiple proposed pathways by which formaldehyde could form. In general, H_2CO could form in the gas phase or on the surfaces of icy grains (or by a combination of both). It is also possible that H_2CO formed in the disk's parent molecular cloud.

Numerous gas phase formation pathways exist (see, e.g., the database discussed by Wakeham et al., 2015). The reaction between atomic oxygen and CH_3 is a well-studied example (Fockenberg & Preses, 2002), but for many of these reactions, the rates are unknown or poorly constrained. Since many of these gas phase reactions are bimolecular, i.e., involve the collision of two molecules, the rates of these reactions are strongly related to the rate of collisions, and therefore the local density. This means that gas phase chemistry is much more efficient close to the star, where the density is high. If the formation of formaldehyde takes place primarily in the gas phase, one should expect the distribution of formaldehyde to be centrally peaked at the location of the star, and fall off steadily with radius.

On the surfaces of grains, formaldehyde is hypothesized to form via the hydrogenation of CO ice (see, e.g., Hiraoka et al., 2002; Watanabe & Kouchi, 2002; Fuchs et al., 2009). If this is the dominant formation pathway, then since H_2CO formed on icy surfaces could in principle thermally or non-thermally desorb into the gas phase (Garrod et al., 2007; Noble et al., 2012), it should be observed to be spatially correlated with the location of CO ice (Qi et al., 2013a).

It is possible to calculate where we expect the thermal desorption of H_2CO to occur, if it forms on grains. Equation 5 in Hollenbach et al. (2009), states that the thermal desorption

temperature, T_d , is given by

$$T_d \simeq \frac{E}{k_B} \left[57 + \ln \left[\left(\frac{N_s}{10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}} \right) \left(\frac{\nu}{10^{13} \text{ Hz}} \right) \left(\frac{1 \text{ cm}^{-3}}{n} \right) \left(\frac{10^4 \text{ cm s}^{-1}}{v} \right) \right] \right]^{-1},$$

where N_s is the cross-sectional density of absorption sites (about 10^{15} cm^{-2}), n is the gas density, v is the thermal speed, and ν is the vibrational frequency of the species in the potential well, given by

$$\nu = 1.6 \times 10^{11} \sqrt{\left(\frac{E}{k} \right) \left(\frac{m}{m_H} \right)} \text{ s}^{-1} = 1.6 \times 10^{11} \sqrt{(2050) \left(\frac{30.026 \text{ u}}{1.008 \text{ u}} \right)} \text{ s}^{-1} \approx 3.95 \times 10^{13} \text{ s}^{-1}.$$

The binding energy of H_2CO is 2050 K (Garrod & Herbst, 2006). Taking the thermal speed to be the most probable particle speed at temperature T , i.e. $v = \sqrt{2kT/m}$, and assuming a gas density of about 10^{10} cm^{-3} , we arrive at a desorption temperature $T_d \sim 40 \text{ K}$. (Varying the gas density by two orders of magnitude produces a change in T_d of only $\sim 4 \text{ K}$ in either direction.)

Pure CO ice is thought to form only in regions of the disk where the temperature drops below 20 K, so one should not expect H_2CO forming on the surfaces of CO ices to thermally desorb in any appreciable quantity. However, it is possible for H_2CO to non-thermally desorb. The UV photodesorption of formaldehyde has been observed in the laboratory by Martín-Doménech et al. (2016) off of ices composed of both pure ethanol and a $\text{H}_2\text{O}:\text{CH}_4$ mixture. Therefore, if grain-surface hydrogenation of CO is the dominant formation pathway of H_2CO , non-thermal desorption should produce gas-phase H_2CO spatially correlated with CO ice, i.e. a ring of emission with no central peak.

Finally, if much of the formaldehyde was inherited from primordial ISM chemistry, it is expected that it would be mixed evenly throughout the disk gas. While subsequent processing by the disk can change the initial constant abundance of such a scenario, to first order, H_2CO would still be observed everywhere in the disk, distinguishing this case from in situ formation.

Previous efforts to observe and constrain the formation of H_2CO have been made. Formaldehyde emission has been spatially resolved in the disks around DM Tau and HD 163296 (Henning & Semenov, 2008; Qi et al., 2013a; Loomis et al., 2015). In HD 163296, formaldehyde is found to form mainly due to grain-surface processes. In DM Tau, both gas and grain chemistries have been invoked to account for the observed emission. These findings may provide a clue as to what one should expect with regard to the formation of H_2CO around other disks, but a priori they could exhibit a drastically different chemistry from either DM Tau or HD 163296.

1.4 TW Hydrae: A Prototypical Disk

Where should one start looking for H_2CO ? For many reasons, TW Hya is the best starting point for understanding protoplanetary disks and their chemistry. At a distance of ~ 54 pc, it is the closest protoplanetary disk to Earth. Its nearly face-on geometry eliminates many degeneracies and complications associated with studying molecular distributions around highly inclined disks. As a result, TW Hya is a particularly well-studied disk: it is one of the few objects for which there is a good estimate of the total disk mass ($\gtrsim 0.06M_\odot$, by Bergin et al., 2013), and it has been shown to possess a host of molecular signatures, including C_2H , OH, HD, N_2H^+ , CS, CN, HCN, DCN, HCO^+ , H^{13}CO^+ , DCO^+ , as well as CO and its isotopologues ^{13}CO and C^{18}O (Bergin et al., 2013; Kastner et al., 1997, 2014, 2015; Qi et al., 2004, 2008, 2013b; Thi et al., 2004). Also, formaldehyde has already been detected toward TW Hya by Qi et al. (2013a), but it was not spatially resolved. The morphology of TW Hya's dust has been the subject of several studies, including those by Menu et al. (2014), Akiyama et al. (2015), Nomura et al. (2015), Rapson et al. (2015), and Debes et al. (2016), to name a few recent ones. TW Hya's density and temperature profiles are also well-constrained. With some caveats, including its old age (~ 10 Myr), TW Hydrae is generally a good prototype for understanding other disks (Öberg, 2015).

Of particular interest to this project, the location of the CO snowline has been measured in TW Hya (Qi et al., 2013b). Therefore, by mapping the distribution of H₂CO and using the predictions made in Section 1.3, a direct comparison between the two can be made to test the importance of formaldehyde’s grain-phase formation pathway.

Therefore, when trying to learn about the chemistry in protoplanetary disks with observations of H₂CO, TW Hya is a terrific option. For the scope of this project, which is limited to studying one object, TW Hya is the natural choice.

1.5 Project Goals and Outline

The main goal of this project is to constrain the major pathway(s) by which H₂CO forms from the observed distribution. In short, we wish to discern between gas-only, grain-only, and gas-grain scenarios.

The first step in this process is to make, process, and interpret observations of TW Hya. In this case we will utilize Atacama Large Millimeter/Submillimeter Array (ALMA) observations (PI: Karin Öberg) of the 3 → 2 transition of H₂CO. In order to understand the observed emission, a set of simulated (or synthetic) observations using six model abundance profiles will be generated for comparison.

To produce synthetic observations, a model of TW Hya’s temperature and density profiles are required. This can then be used as input, along with six different formaldehyde abundance profiles, as input for radiative transfer calculations. Finally, the sky map corresponding to each abundance profile will be run through a task to simulate observations with the same parameters as the real observations, yielding datasets which can be reduced following the same procedure as before. It will be necessary to do a rough scaling of each abundance profile to match the simulated output flux to the observed flux.

After generating a suite of toy models, it will then be possible to exclude some of them based upon how correctly each one predicts the observed emission. By excluding a set of

abundance models, it should be possible to thereby exclude some formation pathways.

Chapter 2 begins with a brief introduction to radio astronomy. It continues with the details and data reduction of the ALMA observations. The data products are then presented and discussed. In Chapter 3, it is shown how the use of radiative transfer calculations and simulated observations allows the choice of a suitable model family for the abundance of H_2CO , and what one can already infer from this choice. Chapter 4 discusses what this project has revealed about formaldehyde's chemistry, and ends with some concluding remarks.

Chapter 2

Observations

2.1 Radio Interferometry

When making observations in the radio band, interferometry is typically used when high spatial resolution is required. In general, the angular resolution θ of a telescope with a single, circular aperture is given by the Rayleigh criterion,

$$\sin \theta = 1.22 \frac{\lambda}{D},$$

where λ is the wavelength of the radiation and D is the diameter of the collecting area. In the limit where $\theta \ll 1$, which is applicable for most astronomical sources, this relation can be approximated as

$$\theta \approx 1.22 \frac{\lambda}{D}.$$

This relation implies that higher angular resolution is achieved by using a larger telescope.

At (sub)millimeter/radio wavelengths, achieving high enough resolution to resolve a target such as a protoplanetary disk is difficult using a single dish instrument, because the required size of the dish is so large. For example, in order to resolve a disk the size of the solar system (with a diameter of ~ 240 AU) in the TW Hydrae association ($d \sim 50$ pc)

observing at a wavelength of 1.2 mm, a single-dish telescope would need a diameter of

$$D \approx 1.22 \frac{\lambda}{\theta} = 1.22 \frac{(1.2 \text{ mm})}{\left(\frac{240 \text{ AU}}{50 \text{ pc}}\right)} = 63 \text{ m},$$

which is about 200 ft—the area of such a dish would be over half that of a football field! Even if one could build such a telescope, the ability to reliably maintain its shape or steer it would present significant obstacles. While large single-dish radio telescopes have been built (the largest steerable radio telescope, the Green Bank Telescope, has a diameter of 100 m), an alternative approach that circumvents such difficulties is the use of radio interferometers, which simulate a large-diameter telescope.

Radio interferometers are designed such that many small-aperture antennas are spread out over a large area and are used together as one instrument. The large distances, or baselines, between the antennas lead to higher angular resolution than each antenna could attain individually. Increasing the distances between antennas probes smaller spatial scales, and placing the antennas closer together probes large spatial scales. Here already one can notice a relative advantage of an interferometer: individual antennas can be placed kilometers apart to probe spatial scales unreachable by single dishes. The process of combining signal from all the antennas together into one simulated aperture is called *aperture synthesis*.

However, aperture synthesis is not perfect. By using antennas spread out over a large area and not using all of that area for collecting radiation, information is lost. It is as if large holes were cut into the dish of a single-aperture telescope: the image will now be degraded in some way. What is the nature of this degradation, and how is this overcome?

To understand how imaging with interferometers is done, it is helpful to introduce the sky brightness $T(\ell, m)$ and visibility $V(u, v)$, which is a complex function. Let (ℓ, m) be a set of two-dimensional coordinates on the plane of the sky, and (u, v) be a set of two-dimensional coordinates on the surface of the Earth. A radio interferometer makes measurements of $V(u, v)$: each pair of antennas in a radio interferometer at a given time samples one point in

the visibility plane. According to the Cittert-Zernike theorem, the visibility function is the two-dimensional Fourier transform of the sky brightness (and vice versa), i.e.

$$V(u, v) = \iint T(\ell, m) e^{-2\pi i(u\ell + vm)} d\ell dm$$

$$T(\ell, m) = \iint V(u, v) e^{2\pi i(u\ell + vm)} du dv,$$

for a certain set of simplifying assumptions (including an extended, quasi-monochromatic, incoherent source; a small field of view; and others — for more detailed information, see Thompson et al., 2001). This relationship means that each sampled visibility contains information about the sky brightness at all (ℓ, m) . An interferometer makes many samples of $V(u, v)$, which can then be Fourier transformed to reconstruct an image of the sky. However, since interferometers can never sample the entire (u, v) plane, $T(\ell, m)$ is never perfectly reconstructed.

How is the (u, v) plane sampled? Each pair of antennas with a unique distance between them gives one value of $V(u, v)$. However, since $T(\ell, m)$ is real, $V(-u, -v) = V^*(u, v)$, so each antenna pair really yields two values of V . As the Earth rotates, the projected baselines between each antenna pair will change in length with respect to the source, so observing over a period of time will allow more $V(u, v)$ values to be measured (this is called Earth rotation synthesis). By adding more antennas to the array, more baseline pairs will exist and so more visibilities can be sampled. Finally, the antennas can be moved around into different configurations to create completely new sets of baseline pairs. Typically these configurations span the range between a very compact arrangement and a very extended arrangement to sample as many different (u, v) points (and spatial scales) as possible—assuming T does not change appreciably with time, observations taken with different configurations on different nights can be combined to give a more complete set of data.

This section was meant to provide a brief introduction to the basics of radio interferometry, and is by no means comprehensive. More information can be found in, for example,

Wilson et al. (2009), Thompson et al. (2001), Sramek & Schwab (1989) and Cornwell & Braun (1989).

2.2 ALMA Observations

The observations of TW Hydrae ($\alpha = 11:01:51.83$, $\delta = -34:42:17.2$) were made by the Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array (ALMA) in Chile (Wootten & Thompson, 2009). At the time of this writing, ALMA represents the state of the art of radio and submillimeter interferometry; it provides unprecedented signal-to-noise and resolution.

The data were taken on 19 Jul 2014 as part of the project 2013.1.00114.S (PI: Karin Öberg), using 32 of ALMA’s 12-m dishes. The baselines, plotted in Figure 2.1, ranged from 34 m to 650 m, and the resulting UV-plane coverage is shown in Figure 2.2. The total time spent on source was about 41 minutes. The synthesized beam measures $0.51'' \times 0.48''$ with a position angle of 93° . TW Hydrae was observed in Band 6 using four spectral windows in the ranges 225.85–225.91 GHz, 227.12–227.18 GHz, 229.51–229.97 GHz, and 241.55–242.01 GHz. The $3_{12} \rightarrow 2_{11}$ line of H_2CO (rest frequency 225.69778 GHz) is located in the first window, which had a frequency resolution of ~ 244 kHz (~ 0.16 km/s).

The $3_{12} \rightarrow 2_{11}$ transition was chosen because of its high intrinsic line strength, as well as its modest lower energy ($E_L \sim 22$ K, Pickett et al., 1998). This means that the transition will not trace only high-temperature material, but rather will be populated across large ranges of the disk.

Figure 2.1 — Antenna positions during observations, denoted by blue triangles. The shortest (34 m) and longest (650 m) baselines are denoted by red lines.

Figure 2.2 — UV-plane coverage. Each “track” of blue points corresponds to one pair of antennas, with each point denoting one integration.

2.3 Data Reduction

Data reduction was carried out using Common Astronomy Software Applications (CASA) package (McMullin et al., 2007), which is developed and maintained by researchers at the National Radio Astronomical Observatory (NRAO), the National Astronomical Observatory

of Japan (NAOJ), the European Southern Observatory (ESO), the CSIRO Australia Telescope National Facility (CSIRO/ATNF), and the Netherlands Institute for Radio Astronomy (ASTRON).

The data were self-calibrated using continuum emission from TW Hydrae. Due to the nature by which the sky image is reconstructed, there is a complicated analogue to the point spread function of optical telescopes called the “dirty beam.” The initial image obtained by performing a naïve Fourier transform on the measured visibilities produces a “dirty image,” which is the sky brightness function convolved with the dirty beam. In order to obtain as close a representation as possible to the sky brightness function $T(\ell, m)$, the image undergoes a `clean` algorithm in CASA.

The `clean` algorithm starts with an empty “Clean Component” list and a residual map initialized to the dirty map, and is carried out as follows:

1. Find the highest peak in the residual map.
2. Subtract a scaled (by the gain) dirty beam from this position from the residual map.
3. Add this peak’s position and amplitude to the Clean Component list.
4. Repeat steps 1–3 until the stopping criterion is reached.

The stopping criterion used in my analysis was to suppress the maximum of the residual map below $\sim 3\sigma_{\text{rms}}$, which is a common criterion for this algorithm. The “clean image” is then reconstructed from the list of Clean Components and is an estimate of $T(\ell, m)$. This process is dependent on the image size, pixel size, weighting scheme used on the visibilities, and other factors. The `clean` algorithm also assumes that the sky brightness function is composed of point sources. The clean image is never anything more than a best estimate of $T(\ell, m)$, but effort is taken to ensure it is as faithful a representation as possible.

2.4 Data Products

When making molecular line observations, there are a series of data products one can produce to emphasize different aspects of the data. Here I present data products which summarize the only spectral line included in this analysis: the *o*-H₂CO 3₁₂ → 2₁₁ line. The dust continuum of the disk is shown in Figure 2.3a, which confirms the position of the disk.

Figure 2.3 — (a) Dust continuum in TW Hydrae, displayed with 5, 10, 20, 40, 80, 160, and 320 times σ_{rms} contours. (b) Moment-zero map, with contours at 3, 5, 7, and 9 times σ_{rms} . (c) Radial profile of H₂CO emission, deprojected and azimuthally averaged using an inclination and position angle quoted by Hughes et al. (2011).

Perhaps the simplest way of summarizing the information gathered in the observations is with a moment-zero map. The moment-zero map collapses the imaged emission in the frequency (velocity) dimension, displaying all the detected formaldehyde line emission in one image. In the moment-zero map shown in Figure 2.3b, the nearly face-on inclination of the disk allows the visual detection of a central gap about 0.5'' in diameter.

If one assumes a disk inclination and position angle, it is possible to deproject the emission in the moment-zero map to the radial dimension. This allows for an easier detection and characterization of ring structures. The inclination ($i = 6^\circ$) and position angle (PA = 155°) values found by Hughes et al. (2011) are used to calculate the radial emission profile, which is displayed in Figure 2.3c (a distance of 54 pc was also assumed). The radial profile clearly

shows a ring of material peaking at $R \simeq 21.6$ AU ($\theta \simeq 0.4''$). It is difficult to constrain the exact size of the gap in H_2CO by eye due to the size of the beam. The size of the gap will be discussed further in Section 3.5.

It is also illustrative to collapse the emission in the spatial dimension to produce a spectrum. Figure 2.4 shows a double-peaked spectrum centered around the relative velocity of the source with respect to the solar system, which one would expect to observe for a disk. The lack of a large asymmetry in the spectrum is consistent with the assumptions about azimuthal symmetry. This spectrum is included for completeness and as a check on the conclusions drawn from the other figures.

The inclusion of a spectrum produced by an interferometer summarizes the total observed flux from a spectral line and the signal-to-noise ratio of the observations. It is also a useful comparison point for single-dish observations.

Figure 2.4 — Spectrum of formaldehyde emission (blue curve). The filled-in velocity channels are plotted in Figure 2.5. The continuum fit has been subtracted out, so a grey dotted line at zero flux density is shown to aid the eye when examining the residuals.

The channel map displays the line emission observed in each velocity channel in separate panels (Figure 2.5). Channel maps are especially useful for observations of protoplanetary disks because they very clearly show the disk’s velocity structure.

Figure 2.5 — Channel map of formaldehyde emission around TW Hydrae.

The panels corresponding to 2.64 km s^{-1} and 2.96 km s^{-1} are not mirror images of each other, so the bulk velocity of TW Hya with respect to the Solar System is likely between 2.80 km s^{-1} and 2.96 km s^{-1} judging by the angles of the emission.

Chapter 3

Toy Models

In the previous chapter, we saw that observing a molecular transition in a disk is no easy task. Making a model for such observations will also turn out to be a difficult undertaking, requiring considerable computation. Therefore, instead of proceeding directly to a quantitative fit to the observations, this chapter is dedicated to constructing toy models of a protoplanetary disk. This will allow the straightforward presentation of the basic concepts associated with a disk model, and will pave the way for future efforts to make a fit of the observations. The toy models developed in this chapter will be sufficient to constrain the formation of formaldehyde in a meaningful way.

Creating a set of model observations requires the modeling of several aspects of the observed disk. The first step in reconstructing the emission from a molecular transition is to choose a physical model of the disk. The most important components of the physical model are the density and temperature structures. For an azimuthally symmetric disk, the density and temperature can be parameterized in cylindrical coordinates for a cross-section of the disk: $T = T(r, z)$, $\rho = \rho(r, z)$. Rotational transitions necessarily originate only from gas-phase molecules (molecules bound in solids cannot freely rotate), so it suffices to model only the density and temperature of the gas phase. It is a standard assumption that the disk is circular and Keplerian, which, along with the host star's mass, determine the disk's velocity structure. The physical structure can then be populated with an abundance profile for the molecule being studied. The “abundance” X of a species A is a dimensionless scaling

of the overall density to the density of the species, i.e. $X = n_A/n_{\text{gas}}$. The gaseous material in a protoplanetary disk is overwhelmingly composed of molecular hydrogen and some helium, so it is convenient to parameterize the disk in terms of the overall gas density and abundance profiles of relatively trace molecules, rather than a set of individual gas densities. In this work, abundance profiles will only vary with radius: $X = X(r)$, although more thorough treatments of disk chemistry can incorporate two-dimensional abundance distributions.

With a physical structure determined, the emission can then be modeled. For each parcel of gas in the disk, its temperature, density, and molecular abundances will determine the population of the energy levels in the relevant molecules and its emission and absorption properties. Photons can be emitted, absorbed, or scattered by each chunk of material, and so to build a picture of the radiation that escapes the disk to the observer, their paths through the disk and the encounters that they undergo are simulated. This is the most computationally expensive phase of the project, and so care must be taken to speed this process up. The simulation of the propagation of photons through the disk draws on methods of *radiative transfer*, which will be discussed more in detail in Section 3.3.

Radiative transfer simulations produce a model sky brightness distribution, but these are not directly comparable to observations. For that to be possible, it is necessary to simulate observations of the proposed brightness distribution. CASA includes a method for doing so: the `simobserve` task. This task “observes” the provided sky brightness using the same parameters as the real observations (antenna configuration, integration time, pointing, airmass, etc.) to produce a set of synthetic observations which are directly comparable to real dataset. By comparing simulated images produced from different abundance model families, the range of plausible models can be narrowed down for a more in-depth investigation.

3.1 Temperature and Density Profiles

Protoplanetary disks exhibit a flared geometry (see, e.g., Kenyon & Hartmann, 1987), which can be understood as follows. At each radius, the vertical extent of the disk is mediated by a balance between gravity and pressure. In a system for which the stellar mass is much greater than the disk mass, the majority of the gravitational pull on disk's material comes from the star. If this is the case, the strength of gravity's pull on material towards the midplane ($z = 0$) decreases with radius. Therefore, the height of the disk will increase with distance from the star.

This behavior is explained by equation of hydrostatic balance, which relates the vertical pressure gradient to the density:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} = -\rho \frac{GM_{\star}}{r^3} z.$$

The solution to this differential equation is of the form

$$\rho \propto \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z}{H(r)} \right)^2 \right],$$

where $H(r)$ is a pressure scale height that increases with increasing radius (see, e.g., Section 5.1.1 of Andrews, 2015). This density profile describes exactly the expected behavior: the density decreases with height at a given radius, and since $H(r)$ increases with r , the curves of constant density flare upwards as they move away from the star.

Understanding the shape of the disk can then inform what one expects the temperature structure to be. The host star is by far the largest regulator of disk temperatures, due to the absorption and processing of its radiation by the disk. Making the simple assumption that the disk absorbs stellar radiation and reradiates it as a blackbody, then equation (1) of Chiang & Goldreich (1997) states that the temperature of the disk will be

$$T \approx \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} \right)^{1/4} \left(\frac{R_{\star}}{r} \right)^{1/2} T_{\star},$$

where r is the radial distance, α is the grazing angle of the incident radiation, and R_\star and T_\star are the stellar radius and effective temperature, respectively. In other words, T will fall with radius as a decreasing power law, and will increase with height.

This is not, however, a satisfactory picture for disks. In reality, only the surface layer of the disk will absorb radiation directly. This layer will then radiate about half the incident radiation to space, and half down into the disk to be processed further. This introduces a different vertical dependence. Another departure from this scenario includes the heating of the disk originating from accretion of material onto the star. This is only important in the very inner disk, i.e. $R \lesssim 2$ AU (D'Alessio et al., 1998). For the purposes here, this region is at small enough distances from the central star that it can be ignored (the angular resolution is not high enough to resolve the very inner portions of the disk).

The blackbody disk model therefore gives us a rough idea of a disk's temperature structure, but we can do better. One common parameterization used for the temperature structure of disks is

$$T_{\text{model}}(r, z) = T_a + (T_m - T_a) \left[\cos \left(\frac{\pi z}{4h_r} \right) \right]^{2\delta},$$

where

$$T_a = T_{a,0} \left(\frac{\sqrt{r^2 + z^2}}{r_0} \right)^{-q_a}; \quad T_m = T_{m,0} \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^{-q_m}; \quad h_r = h_0 \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^{-h}.$$

For $z = 0$, T reduces to the midplane temperature profile, T_m , which is a simple power law—we recover the functional form of the blackbody model, but the index q_m is allowed to differ from $1/2$. As z increases, the atmospheric temperature component T_a comes more and more into play via the cosine term. This form for the temperature profile has been employed successfully in the past: it matches the one used by Andrews et al. (2012) in their parameterization of the temperature structure of TW Hydrae.

To provide reasonable parameters for T_{model} , a rough fit to a grid model of the physical parameters of TW Hydrae developed by Charlie Qi was made. Due to the relative importance of the midplane region for the chemistry of formaldehyde, it was fit to first (Figure 3.1) and

fixed to fit the final three parameters instead of fitting all parameters at once.

Figure 3.1 — Midplane temperature fit to the Qi grid model. While the Qi model shows more structure than a simple power law, it is more straightforward for a toy model to use a simple yet reasonable temperature structure than a more faithful but complicated structure.

While this midplane fit is not perfect, it is only necessary at this point to find reasonable parameters for input into a toy model of the disk. The tradeoff for simplicity over accuracy here is worth the ease of interpretation later. The full set of temperature structure parameters is shown in Table 3.1.

Parameter	Value
$T_{m,0}$	27.31 K
q_m	0.6319
r_0	13.45 AU
h_0	-3.315 AU
h	-1.241
$T_{a,0}$	155.8 K
q_a	0.3229
δ	1.0997

Table 3.1 — Best-fit parameters found for the temperature profile T_{model} .

The density profile was fit using a model of the form

$$\Sigma_{\text{model}}(r, z) = \frac{\Sigma_r}{h_r \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z}{h_r} \right)^2 \right],$$

where

$$\Sigma_r = \Sigma_0 \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^{-\gamma} \exp \left[\frac{r}{r_c} (2 - \gamma) \right]; \quad h_r = h_0 \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^{-h}.$$

This matches the form of the solution to the hydrostatic equation discussed above. Again, the midplane profile was fit independently and fixed (Figure 3.2) before performing a fit over the remaining parameters. This is a good fit, and is definitely suitable for use in toy models. The full set of parameters is shown in Table 3.2.

Figure 3.2 — Midplane density fit to the Qi grid model.

Parameter	Value
γ	1.442
r_c	6.238 AU
r_0	4.750 AU
h_0	0.8272 AU
h	-0.7183

Table 3.2 — Best-fit parameters found for the density profile.

3.2 Abundance Profiles

A simple family of abundance profile models are used to illuminate the nonlinear relationship between abundance and radiative intensity, as well as to provide clear interpretation. Six profiles were considered: a flat profile, a decreasing power law, and an increasing power law, each with and without a central gap. The power laws had indices of ± 2 . The models were normalized such that the peak simulated flux observed matched the peak flux of the observations (see Section 3.4).

Figure 3.3 — Abundance profile models. Panels (a), (b), and (c) show flat, decreasing power law, and increasing power law abundance models, respectively. Panels (d), (e), and (f) show the same respective model shapes with a 15 AU inner gap, renormalized to the peak flux.

3.3 Radiative Transfer

As previously discussed, the observed shape and intensity of the radiation produced by a molecular transition in a protoplanetary disk depend on several factors. Some of the most important are the density and temperature structure of the disk, as well as the abundance profile of the species in question. Photons originating from a small chunk of embedded material in the disk, for example, must travel through a non-negligible amount of material before reaching the observer, potentially being scattered or absorbed along the way. Since the temperature, density, and abundance values at each disk location will affect the local

emission, absorption, and scattering properties, it is easy to imagine how complicated it is to account for all the radiation produced by the species in question throughout the disk. The process by which one accounts for this radiation is known as *radiative transfer*.

A quantitative understanding of the production and processing of radiation is given by the *radiative transfer equation*:

$$\frac{dI_\nu}{ds} = j_\nu - \alpha_\nu I_\nu$$

where I_ν is the intensity of the radiation, j_ν is the emissivity of the material, α_ν is the absorption coefficient of the material, and s is a spatial coordinate along the direction of the radiation (the ν subscript denotes a dependence on frequency). This equation states that the change in the intensity of radiation in a certain direction per unit length (dI_ν/ds) is increased by the emission of the material it passes through (j_ν) and decreased by the amount of radiation absorbed by that material, which is proportional to the incoming radiation ($\alpha_\nu I_\nu$). In a radiative transfer calculation, a disk's temperature, density, abundance, and velocity profiles are modeled, and photons are propagated through the disk and processed using the radiative transfer equation.

In this work, the radiative transfer code LIME (Line Modeling Engine, available at <https://github.com/lime-rt/lime>, see Brinch & Hogerheijde, 2010) is used to make these calculations. LIME's capabilities include non-LTE considerations, as well as the use of De-launay grids instead of regular grids to efficiently and robustly calculate radiation originating from different regions of the disk. A considerable savings in computation time is made by using input profiles that are parametric, which is why it was worthwhile to do so in Sections 3.1 and 3.2.

Non-LTE conditions arise when the spontaneous de-excitation of molecules of a given species begins to become more important than collisional de-excitation. This typically occurs in disks where the density and temperature drop sufficiently enough to decrease collisional rates below a certain threshold, which depends on the species in question. Since H₂CO possesses a strong dipole, spontaneous de-excitation of the observed transition will dominate

in regions of the disk where $n \lesssim 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ over a wide range of temperatures (Shirley, 2015). Since we cannot a priori know that no formaldehyde exists in such regions, it is important that non-LTE calculations are made using LIME, which are presented in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4 — LIME output for the abundance profiles shown in Figure 3.3, to be used as input for synthetic observations. The flux density per pixel of these panels is scaled so that the simulated observations (Figure 3.5) match the observed peak flux.

3.4 Synthetic Observations

Simulated ALMA observations were computed from the averaged LIME-produced FITS images using the CASA routine `simobserve`. Antenna configuration data from the night of observations (visible in Figure 2.1) was used to reconstruct observations as faithfully as possible, and the same process was used to clean the images and produce moment-zero maps, shown in Figure 3.5. While it is possible to include sky noise in the simulations, that is not

done here to ease interpretation and allow the comparison of abundance profiles with the same peak flux.

Figure 3.5 — Simulated ALMA observations, using the abundance profiles from Figure 3.3.

No sky noise is simulated to provide ease of interpretation. The peak flux of each approximately matches the peak flux of the observations.

The first result we can infer is that the models shown in panels (a), (b), and (c) all exhibit centrally peaked emission, and harbor too much flux very close to the star. Only a model with a central gap will be able to reproduce a similar radial profile as Figure 2.3c, so models (a), (b), and (c) are easily excluded. Model (e) is unable to reproduce the extent of the observed emission, and scaling the abundance higher to match the extent of the emission results in an overall flux that is too high. Models (d) and (f) show similar emission, and seem like good matches to the data. Since the inner radius is the main parameter of interest, model (d) is a better candidate than model (f). This is because the inner radius is more well-defined for a flat profile than for a profile which already tapers off at low radii. The

strength and width of peak emission is also better matched by model (d), as well as the slope of the radial profile (see Figure 3.7). Thus I conclude that the best abundance profile to use in modeling H₂CO for the stated purposes is a flat profile with a central gap.

Although we can identify an abundance profile that more closely resembles the observations than the other five, the use of toy models to make statements about the observations has strong limitations which are important to recognize. The temperature and density profiles are not guaranteed to be accurate. In fact, one possible explanation for the underprediction of emission in the outer disk is that T_{model} is too low—the absence of large dust grains at larger radii could lead to a decreased opacity and deeper photon and CR penetration. Another large assumption that these toy models incorporate is a constant abundance with height. In reality, formaldehyde is thought to form in a well-delineated atmospheric layer (Figure 3 of Loomis et al., 2015, provides an illustrative example), though this is not certain. A thin layer of H₂CO at a higher average temperature would lead to more extended emission than the abundance distribution used for the models here, which is another possible explanation for the underprediction. In any case, there is no good motivation for extracting much physical meaning from the vertically constant abundance profile which best matches the observations. The underprediction in the outer disk is not due to too small an outer radius (70 AU), as is clearly seen in Figure 3.4.

Therefore, the most important parameter to constrain using the toy models is the inner radius of H₂CO production—this will reveal the most information about formaldehyde’s formation pathway. With a functional form selected, we can generate a few more synthetic observations to make some statements about the data. Figure 3.5d displays the model which uses an inner radius of 15 AU. Models with inner radii of 10 AU and 20 AU are also generated and displayed in Figure 3.6 along with the observations. Radial profiles of the emission in Figure 3.6 are shown together in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.6 — Moment-zero map and simulated moment-zero maps of TW Hya in H₂CO, using the abundance profile from Figure 3.3d with different inner radii. Panel (a) shows the dataset, and panels (b), (c), and (d) show simulations using inner radii of 10 AU, 15 AU, and 20 AU, respectively. No sky noise is simulated to provide ease of interpretation.

Figure 3.7 — Deprojected radial profiles of the moment-zero maps in Figure 3.6. The profile of the observations (the same curve as Figure 2.3c) is plotted as a dotted black line. The grey scale bar denotes the effective radius of the synthesized beam, $\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{b_{\text{maj}}b_{\text{min}}}$, to provide a sense of the amount the emission is radially smeared.

Figures 3.6 and 3.7 make the case that R_{in} is likely $\gtrsim 15$ AU. By eye, Figure 3.6c shows that an inner radius of 20 AU is too large. The beam smearing of the central gap is best reproduced by the model in Figure 3.6b, and the radial profile is also best matched by this

model. It is worth noting that all three toy models match the slope of the H₂CO radial profile emission outside of the peak, arguing for a flat profile over a power law profile.

While Figures 3.6 and 3.7 do not definitively yield an inner radius of H₂CO, they do provide the useful constraint that it is close to 15 AU, or at least between 15 AU and 20 AU. Even though this is not a precise measurement, it will be sufficient for the purposes of this project, as we will see in the next chapter. Considering that this determination was made with fiducial models and not quantitatively, I estimate that the error associated with the value of R_{in} is on the order of 5 AU, so a more precise statement cannot be made.

Chapter 4

Discussion and Conclusions

4.1 Formation Pathway of Formaldehyde

Recalling the discussion in Section 1.3, we are now able to assess the likelihood of gas, grain, and primordial H_2CO formation cases.

Gas-phase interactions can be excluded as the primary formation mechanism. The emission is not centrally peaked, as would be case in a gas-only scenario, and the best fiducial model excludes any regions of the disk in which gas-phase chemistry would be efficient, predicting a gap on the order of 15 AU. Accounting for beam smearing, Figure 3.6 makes the case that there is little to no H_2CO emission originating from $R \lesssim 10$ AU. At this radius, gas temperatures and densities have already dropped low enough that no gas-gas interactions can take place efficiently. All observed H_2CO can be explained without invoking any gas-phase chemistry, but we cannot confidently place an upper limit on such a contribution. Future work (see Section 4.5) using the velocity information and not just the moment-zero map would be able to place such a limit.

It is very likely that the bulk of the observed H_2CO in TW Hya was produced entirely in the disk, and not inherited from molecular cloud chemistry. In such a scenario, considered by Willacy (2007), the H_2CO would appear coincidentally with gaseous CO in the inner disk. Qi et al. (2013b) report the presence of CO gas throughout the disk, so H_2CO is not evenly mixed into the gas and must be produced in situ.

Grain-surface chemistry seems to be the primary pathway by which H_2CO forms. The sharp inner radius is suggestive of a chemistry which turns on coincident with the availability of ices on grain surfaces. Multiple grain-surface pathways exist, including (1) the hydrogenation of CO, (2) processing of $\text{CH}_4:\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ice, and (3) photodesorption of CH_3OH ice (scenarios (2) and (3) are described in Martín-Doménech et al., 2016). Pathway (1) should produce H_2CO coincident with the presence of CO ice. Considering pathway (2), if H_2CO desorbs along with the H_2O ice in which it forms, it should be observed starting in the inner disk ($R \gtrsim 4$ AU). However, CH_4 is not entirely trapped by water ice, and so this assumption likely does not hold throughout the disk. Without chemical modeling, we are unable to completely rule out this formation pathway. If H_2CO forms via pathway (3), then H_2CO should appear where methanol is desorbing. One can use the binding energy of CH_3OH (5530 K, according to Garrod & Herbst, 2006) to compute that this would occur in TW Hya at a radius close to 1 AU, so by the same logic, pathway (3) is not a viable explanation of the data.

Since the CO snowline has been directly measured in TW Hya, we can directly compare its location to the spatial distribution of H_2CO to assess the likelihood of pathway (1).

4.2 Comparison with CO Snowline Location

In comparing the location of formaldehyde to the location CO ice, it is important to understand how the latter is measured. The location of the CO snowline cannot be measured by observing CO gas. Since CO is highly abundant in disks, the upper layers will always contain gaseous CO. Since the rotational transitions of CO are extremely strong (and optically thick), observations of CO gas in disks only ever trace the warm surface layers. To circumvent this, the CO snowline is measured by observing gaseous N_2H^+ . In the presence of CO gas, N_2H^+ gas is very efficiently destroyed, so N_2H^+ is only present where CO has completely frozen out.

Using this method, the location of the CO snowline was measured by Qi et al. (2013b) to

be between 28 and 31 AU (at 3σ). This range is the outer ring marked in Figure 4.1. Much of the formaldehyde emission originates from well inside the CO snowline. As the emission is indicative of grain-surface chemistry, and hydrogenation of CO is the only remaining grain-surface formation pathway that is plausible, how can we explain the emission inside of $r \sim 30$ AU?

Figure 4.1 — Same as Figure 3.6, but with rings overplotted which correspond to the CO snowline as measured by Qi et al. (2013b) (3σ confidence, outer ring) and the expected radius that CO begins to freeze out onto water ices (inner ring).

Emission inside the nominal CO snowline could be accounted for by CO ice inside 30 AU, i.e., in the presence of CO gas. The N_2H^+ line measured by Qi et al. (2013b) is the location of *total* freeze-out of CO ice in the midplane. Outside of this radius, CO is freezing onto ices that are already mostly composed of CO. The associated binding energy of this interaction is about 866 K (Fayolle et al., 2016). However, the binding energy of CO freezing onto ices composed of mostly H_2O is considerably higher, ranging from 1155 K to 1575 K as measured in the laboratory by Fayolle et al. (2016). This corresponds to a temperature range of 28–38 K. According to the temperature fit described in Section 3.1, the midplane reaches this range of temperatures between 8–13 AU (this range is denoted by the inner ring plotted in Figure 4.1).

This 8–13 AU range for the start of H_2CO formation is almost certainly too low. Following the same calculations for pure CO ice formation using the binding energy 866 K yields

a calculated CO snowline radius of ~ 23 AU. Since the CO snowline is directly measured to be at 30 AU, it should be expected that the assumed temperature structure is causing these underpredictions, and that H₂CO production should turn on outside of 13 AU. Indeed, the temperature model of TW Hya is relatively uncertain, and several different temperature models have been invoked to describe TW Hya (as described in Bergin et al., 2013). Accounting for the temperature model, this is consistent with the value of $R_{\text{in}} \gtrsim 15$ AU determined above, and provides an answer to how formaldehyde can form inside the CO snowline.

4.3 Comparison with Dust Location

Having explained the observed inner radius of H₂CO, we turn to the observed outer radius. Since H₂CO is forming on dust grains, then we should expect the emission to decrease where there are no longer any large (millimeter-sized) grains. However, outside of this radius at which this occurs (R_{dust}), small grains coupled to the gas will still produce H₂CO, so the emission should not disappear. In fact, the lack of millimeter-sized grains could decrease the opacity in the outer disk, and may therefore lead to a slight bump in the radial profile due to an increased photodesorption rate.

The distribution of large dust grains has a sharp cutoff at 60 AU as measured by Andrews et al. (2012). Examining the radial profile (black dotted curve in Figure 3.7), we notice the emission cuts off (to an order of the effective beam radius) near this radius, and there is a slope change which becomes apparent at $R \simeq 50$ AU which could correspond to the decreased opacity of the disk. This matches the above predictions, and therefore the emission in the outer disk is also consistent with a grain-surface formation pathway.

4.4 Conclusions

The formation of formaldehyde in TW Hya has been shown to occur on grain surfaces as a product of the hydrogenation of CO. Formaldehyde exists in a ring with $R_{\text{in}} \gtrsim 15$ AU, with gas-phase reactions seemingly unimportant. The distribution is consistent with laboratory experiments of CO freeze-out and dust continuum observations. What remains to be seen is how unique this chemistry is to TW Hya. This scenario matches what has been inferred from H_2CO and N_2H^+ observations of the Herbig Ae star HD 163296. However, the results for TW Hya differ from the H_2CO chemistry of DM Tau, which hosts a centrally peaked component attributed to gas-phase formation.

An intuitive explanation for the difference in chemistry between these two disks is their relative ages: TW Hya (age ~ 10 Myr) is at least a few Myr older than DM Tau (Simon et al., 2000, age $\sim 3\text{--}7$ Myr). Since older disks have typically undergone more clearing out of gas, it is probable that the remaining gas density is not high enough for efficient production of H_2CO . If this is the dominant effect, it would imply that gas-phase chemistry was more important in TW Hya’s history.

However, there are several other potential explanations for the difference in H_2CO chemistry between TW Hya and DM Tau. Unlike TW Hya, DM Tau has a large inner gap ($R_{\text{gap}} \sim 19$ AU) in large grains (Andrews et al., 2011), which could lower the opacity in the inner disk and raise temperatures, thereby increasing the importance of gas-phase chemistry. TW Hya is also known to be carbon-depleted in the gas phase (Favre et al., 2013; Kama et al., 2016), and so perhaps the limiting factor on gas pathways is the lack of gas-phase carbon. In principle, the accretion rate and stellar activity could contribute to differences in gas-phase chemistry, especially considering that such reactions would take place in close proximity to the star.

4.5 Future Work

There is still much to be learned from this dataset. The models developed in Chapter 3 now allow an appropriate range of parameters to be chosen for a quantitative fit to the emission. Chemical modeling, as well as observations of more transitions of H_2CO , can be incorporated to constrain the vertical structure and obtain a more reasonable abundance profile. The analysis presented in this work was limited by the spatial resolution of the synthesized beam, and a more in-depth modeling of the disk, assuming Keplerian rotation of the disk, can utilize the velocity structure to constrain the location of H_2CO down to a few AU.

From spatially resolved H_2CO observations of only a handful of T Tauri stars, it is not possible to definitively determine which of these factors accounts for the difference in H_2CO chemistry. Future observations of disks can help break these degeneracies. Formaldehyde has been detected towards disks other than the three discussed above, and so the prospects of future ALMA observations to investigate this question further are optimistic.

If spatially resolved H_2CO and N_2H^+ observations are made of a larger population of disks, it will be possible to determine if H_2CO production—paving the way for further chemistry—occurs only in a subset of these planet-forming systems, or ubiquitously.

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